

PLANMAP: Geological mapping supporting the exploration of the Moon, Mars, and Mercury
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Geologic mapping key to many elements of planetary exploration, ranging from mission planning, orbital and rover reconnaissance, the reconstruction of local to global planetary geologic histories and multi-scale characterisation and selection of landing sites and sample analyses.

PLANMAP aims at producing geologic maps with the widest possible range of underlying data sources, including imagery, topography, hyperspectral, and geophysical data, as well as direct or indirect three-dimensional information, in order to produce surface and subsurface geologic models of planetary surfaces at local and regional scales, both from orbital and lander/rover platforms.

Mapping products at various level of maturity and development are available on the Planmap data portal as both files, web-accessible maps and OGC endpoints for both desktop and programmatic access on <https://data.planmap.eu/> and <https://maps.planmap.eu/>.

Planmap code and utilities are going to be available on <https://github.com/planmap-eu>.

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